

Editorial

Changes of the Coastal Zones Due to Climate Change

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“Changes of the Coastal Zones Due to Climate Change” explores the complex relationship between coastal climate change and sea dynamics while placing the research within a broader context of climate change and its effects on coastal ecosystems. The overarching objectives of this Special Issue are twofold: first, to enhance our understanding of the complexities of climate change in coastal areas, and second, to develop valuable insights to mitigate consequences and foster adaptation strategies for vulnerable regions.

Within the context of climate change research, coastal areas are of particular concern due to their high susceptibility to environmental shifts. Rising sea levels, alterations in precipitation patterns, and the intensification of extreme weather events are some of the pressing challenges faced by coastal communities worldwide. Consequently, coastal ecosystems, marine biodiversity, infrastructure, and human settlements are vulnerable to the impacts of these changes. References [1,2] aim to investigate and address these concerns, providing valuable scientific evidence to aid in the development of comprehensive coastal zone management and climate adaptation plans.

References [3,4] provide valuable information on various aspects of coastal climate change and sea–land dynamics in diverse geographic settings and identify tools and methods to be used in the implementation of socioeconomic adaptation strategies. The results of [5] showcase tools to explore the potential for renewable offshore energy exploitation. One of the central research objectives is to analyze the impacts of climate change on storm surge inundation, coastal flooding, and shoreline changes. The combination of rising sea levels and extreme weather events poses a significant threat to coastal regions, particularly low-lying areas.

Apostolopoulos et al. [1] investigate the use of remote sensing tools to monitor changes in critical parameters affecting the spatiotemporal coastline evolution of a protected ecosystem. The authors modeled the erosion–accretion cycle in the past decades to date and monitored the long-term changes in the Prokopos Lagoon shoreline in the Peloponnese area.

Understanding the spatial and temporal variability of waves and storm surges is crucial to develop effective strategies to mitigate the risks associated with coastal flooding [2]. By assessing the current and future levels of coastal flooding, Paranunzio et al. [2] aim to provide an integrated risk assessment accounting for the exposure and socioeconomic vulnerability of the interested areas. These aspects can guide the development of informed policies to safeguard coastal communities and ecosystems.

Another critical focus of one of the research papers from this Special Issue is the investigation of sea-breeze fronts in the Baltic Sea climate, with specific attention to the case of Lithuania, as studied by Dailidė et al. [3]. Sea-breeze fronts play pivotal roles in shaping local weather patterns and are influenced by changes in sea–land dynamics and coastal climatic conditions. Leveraging remote sensing methods enhances the accuracy and precision of studying these sea-breeze fronts, providing essential data for climate modeling and informed coastal planning. The insights gained from these studies can help us predict

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changes in local weather patterns, understand climate variability, and anticipate potential impacts on coastal environments.

Riera-Spiegelhalder et al. [4] review ecosystem-based solutions and other strategies for the socioeconomic assessment of the adaptation to climate change in coastal areas. The authors show the benefits of such natural-based measures compared to hard- and soft-based approaches.

O’Connell et al. [5] showcase the development of a comprehensive geospatial dataset and a Web-GIS tool for assessing ocean energy site suitability in Ireland and Western UK waters. Identifying extensive areas in the Atlantic Ocean and Celtic Sea that are appropriate for wave energy deployment highlights the potential of utilizing renewable energy in these regions. This contributes to understanding the evolving coastal dynamics in response to climate change. This study identifies less extensive areas that are suitable for tidal energy deployment, providing valuable information for the sustainable development of ocean energy resources in the Irish Sea and Inner Seas off the West Coast of Scotland, which are undergoing changing coastal conditions due to climate change [5].

In conclusion, the Special Issue on “Changes of the Coastal Zones Due to Climate Change” strives to advance our knowledge of the interactions between coastal climate change and sea–land dynamics to create sustainable solutions and adaptation strategies to cope with natural hazards within the broader context of the impacts of climate change on coastal regions, while exploring tools to assess the potential for services in key economic sectors (e.g., renewable energy). The findings of the research papers included in this Special Issue contribute to a comprehensive understanding of coastal climate dynamics, enabling policymakers, researchers, and stakeholders to make informed decisions that foster resilience and sustainability in the face of an evolving climate.

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References

1. Riera-Spiegelhalder, M.; Campos-Rodrigues, L.; Enseñado, E.M.; Dekker-Arlain, J.d.; Papadopoulou, O.; Arampatzis, S.; Vervoort, K. Socioeconomic Assessment of Ecosystem-Based and Other Adaptation Strategies in Coastal Areas: A Systematic Review. *J. Mar. Sci. Eng.* **2023**, *11*, 319. [[CrossRef](#)]
2. Paranunzio, R.; Guerrini, M.; Dwyer, E.; Alexander, P.J.; O’Dwyer, B. Assessing Coastal Flood Risk in a Changing Climate for Dublin, Ireland. *J. Mar. Sci. Eng.* **2022**, *10*, 1715. [[CrossRef](#)]
3. Dailidė, R.; Dailidė, G.; Razbadauskaitė-Venskė, I.; Povilanskas, R.; Dailidienė, I. Sea-Breeze Front Research Based on Remote Sensing Methods in Coastal Baltic Sea Climate: Case of Lithuania. *J. Mar. Sci. Eng.* **2022**, *10*, 1779. [[CrossRef](#)]
4. Apostolopoulos, D.N.; Avramidis, P.; Nikolakopoulos, K.G. Estimating Quantitative Morphometric Parameters and Spatiotemporal Evolution of the Prokopos Lagoon Using Remote Sensing Techniques. *J. Mar. Sci. Eng.* **2022**, *10*, 931. [[CrossRef](#)]
5. O’Connell, R.; Furlong, R.; Guerrini, M.; Cullinane, M.; Murphy, J. Development and Application of a GIS for Identifying Areas for Ocean Energy Deployment in Irish and Western UK Waters. *J. Mar. Sci. Eng.* **2023**, *11*, 826. [[CrossRef](#)]

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